

Quadrature-Based Credible Set Estimation for Radar Feature Extraction

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Abstract—Efficient and accurate extraction of physically-relevant features from measured radar data is desirable for automatic target recognition (ATR). In this paper, we present an estimation technique to find credible sets of parameters for any given feature model. The proposed approach provides parameter estimates along with confidence values. Maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimates provide a single (vector) parameter value, typically found via sampling methods. However, computational inefficiency and inaccuracy issues commonly arise when sampling multi-modal or multi-dimensional posteriors. As an alternative, we use Gaussian quadrature to compute probability mass functions, covering the entire probability space. An efficient zoom-in approach is used to iteratively locate regions of high probability. The (possibly disjoint) regions of high probability correspond to sets of feasible parameter values, call credible sets. Thus, our quadrature-based credible set estimator (QBCSE) includes values very near the true parameter and confuser values that may lie far from the true parameter but map with high probability to the same observed data. The credible set and associated probabilities are computed and should both be passed to an ATR algorithm for informed decision-making. Applicable to any feature model, we demonstrate the proposed QBCSE scheme using canonical shape feature models in synthetic aperture radar phase history.

Index Terms—radar feature extraction, Bayesian estimation, credible set, quadrature, automatic target recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

Previously, Bayesian approaches have been applied to radar feature extraction and matching for ATR [1]–[3]. Bayesian estimates are beneficial because the posterior probability density function (pdf) provides a likelihood value that may be associated with a parameter estimate, e.g. the maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimator. It is desirable to track both decisions and uncertainty along the entire data collection and processing chain [3], [4], as shown in Figure 1. In this work, we focus on the feature extraction block, with results being the extracted canonical feature parameters and associated confidences. We present an estimation technique from [5], [6] to find all credible sets of parameters and their associated probabilities. The proposed approach provides estimated parameter values along with confidence values for use in Bayesian ATR schemes. The approach is demonstrated on canonical shape scatterers from [7].

Unlike a traditional maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimator which returns a single (scalar or vector) parameter value, the

Fig. 1. Uncertainties tracked through data collection, parameter estimation, and detection/discrimination decisions provide value-added information.

proposed quadrature-based credible set estimator (QBCSE) returns sets of all feasible parameters. In some cases, the credible set (CS) will be a *credible interval* [8], [9] around the true parameter. In other cases, the CS will be sets of credible intervals around the true parameter and around other parameter sets that map to the observed data. For example, the CS will capture when, for practical flight paths discussed in [10], measured phase history data maps to multiple, feasible canonical feature representations. The QBCSE avoids sampling issues associated with numerical computation of MAP estimates and accounts for multiple highly likely solutions, including the case of a multi-modal posterior pdf. It will be up to the target discrimination algorithm to interpret and act on the extracted features and uncertainty information provided by the estimator.

It should be noted, that quadrature integration and subregion adaptive integration techniques have been discussed before (see [11]), but emphasis was placed on sampling due to the “curse of dimensionality” with quadrature methods. With the advent of modern computing resources and need for estimation in higher dimensions, quadrature is becoming more attractive. Thus, we develop the QBCSE with a radar feature extraction application in mind. Section II defines the QBCSE and compares it to a MAP estimator. Section III discusses a fast implementation of the QBCSE that utilizes grid search and a graphics processor unit (GPU). Section IV shows example results. Section V draws conclusions.

II. CREDIBLE SET ESTIMATOR

The estimation and uncertainty framework depicted in Figure 1 is naturally fulfilled with a Bayesian scheme that provides both parameter estimates (e.g. from a MAP estimator)

and the associated uncertainty (e.g. a posterior probability density function (pdf)). For parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_M]^T$ and observed data vector \mathbf{y} , the MAP estimator is given by the parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ that maximizes the posterior pdf

$$p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{y}) = \frac{p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})p(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})p(\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta}}. \quad (1)$$

In practical applications, (1) often does not have a closed-form solution; the MAP estimator is found by sampling the parameter space and locating the maximizer of the numerator term. Accuracy of the MAP estimate is limited by the sample spacing. If sampling is too coarse, especially over a multi-dimensional space, regions of high probability may be missed. Too fine of sampling causes prohibitively large computational memory and time resources. The computational burden further increases if accurate computation of the denominator term is needed to obtain the posterior pdf along with the parameter estimate. Sampling and computation issues grow exponentially with the size of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

For the case of detecting a signal in additive white Gaussian noise, the denominator in (1) becomes an infinite (multi-dimensional) integral of a weighted Gaussian function, for which a closed-form solution exists only for a small set of weight functions. A sampling approach to integration is inherently finite and will cut off the tails of any distribution with infinite domain. We desire maximum flexibility in the weight function (the prior distribution $p(\boldsymbol{\theta})$). As shown in the next section, the denominator integral in (1) can be approximated with predictable accuracy using quadrature techniques.

Another drawback of the MAP estimator is that MAP uses a hit-or-miss cost function,

$$C_{\text{MAP}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{true}} \\ 1 & \boldsymbol{\theta} \neq \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{true}} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

penalizing even practical solutions that may be “close enough” to the true parameter for the application at hand. CS estimation (CSE) remedies the drawbacks of MAP by formulating a new cost function. QBCSE treats the problem as discrete probability mass intervals rather than a sampled posterior pdf problem.

CSE relaxes the hit-or-miss cost to [5]

$$C_{\text{CSE}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \boldsymbol{\theta} \in \{\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{credible}}\} \\ 1 & \boldsymbol{\theta} \notin \{\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{credible}}\} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

such that CSE does not penalize parameter estimates within a *credible set*. A credible set is defined as the smallest set $\{\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{credible}}\}$ of parameter values $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ such that [8], [9]

$$\int_{\{\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{credible}}(\mathbf{y})\}} p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{y})d\boldsymbol{\theta} = 1 - \alpha. \quad (4)$$

That is, $\{\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{credible}}\}$ is the $100(1-\alpha)\%$ highest posterior density (HPD) “subset of the sample space of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ where the posterior density of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is maximized” [9]. Thus, we seek the set of parameters corresponding to posterior pdf values above some threshold τ . The credible set, or HPD, “will be a regular interval if the posterior distribution is unimodal, and it may

be a discontinuous region if the posterior distribution is multi-modal” [9]. In practice, the vast majority of examples we have found in statistics literature have been scalar parameter estimation problems in which the credible set is a one-dimensional interval. For radar estimation problems, it is common to have many dimensions and multi-modal posteriors (e.g. due to phase-wrapping or layover effects). Thus, there is a need to refine development of the multi-dimensional, multi-modal generalization of the credible set.

ATR performance metrics in [12], [13] are computed as one-dimensional ($\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is a scalar) contiguous confidence intervals covering the proportion or rate parameter of interest. We treat the general problem of finding discontinuous credible sets for the multi-dimensional ($\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is a vector) problem. The credible set formalizes the notion of “close enough” in the estimator cost function, allowing the user to set a desired level of accuracy in the estimate. CSE allows for disjoint regions of parameter space to have zero cost, a property that is especially useful for radar canonical shape estimation, where multiple shapes and/or parameter sets may yield similar scattering responses.

Finding peaks and credible sets in the posterior density $p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{y})$ can be viewed as finding intervals of large probability mass. Rather than compute the posterior pdf, we compute the posterior probability mass function

$$P_i = P(\mathbf{a}_i \leq \boldsymbol{\theta} < \mathbf{b}_i) = \int_{\mathbf{a}_i}^{\mathbf{b}_i} p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{y})d\boldsymbol{\theta}, \quad (5)$$

over integration limits indexed by i , with controllable accuracy using Gaussian quadrature techniques [5], [14], [15]. Thus, we implement a QBCSE. All probability within the integration limits is accounted for, up to the error of the numerical integration method, and highly likely solutions will not be missed due to coarse sampling of parameter space. The credible set $\{\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{credible}}\}$ is a set of the largest masses

$$\begin{aligned} \{\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{credible}}\} &= \{\mathbf{a}_i \leq \boldsymbol{\theta} < \mathbf{b}_i \text{ corresponding to the largest } P_i \\ &\text{such that } \sum P_i = 1 - \alpha\}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $1-\alpha$ is a desired confidence level, e.g. 95% confidence. Equation (6) is the pmf version of (4).

Equation (5) is, in general, a multi-dimensional integral. However, rather than sampling the entire multi-dimensional space, we need only break the space into regions, integrate, locate regions of large probability mass, zoom in on those regions, and repeat for new integration limits. Figure 2 provides a notional example where darker colors indicate higher probability. QBCSE locates the MAP estimate in the limit as integration limits converge to the true parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{true}}$. In addition, QBCSE provides all *credible* solutions, dictated by a user’s desired confidence α . Some credible solutions may reside near $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{true}}$ in parameter space and others may reside in another region, disjoint from $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{true}}$, as indicated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Notional example of locating the credible set for a multi-modal posterior pdf. Probability masses may be computed first on a larger grid, then zoomed in on regions of high probability, as indicated by the grid lines.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Methodology

The computation of pmfs P_i lends itself to a grid search method and parallel processing to locate regions of high probability. Beginning with a few large integration limit intervals (ILIs) $[a_i, b_i]$, (5) is computed to coarsely determine regions of high probability in parameter space. Each ILI that has a large probability mass is divided into sub-intervals (sub-ILIs) and their respective probability masses are calculated. Sub-ILIs of low mass are discarded from further study, though the estimated mass is retained for proper probability scaling. The process is repeated until a user-specified sub-ILI size is reached. HPD regions are located in the pmf computed at the smallest sub-ILI size and included in the credible set. The algorithm is summarized in Figure 3.

Expanding (5) as

$$P_i = \int_{a_i}^{b_i} p(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathbf{y}) d\boldsymbol{\theta} = \frac{\int_{\theta_{1,i}} \cdots \int_{\theta_{M,i}} p(\mathbf{y} | \theta_1, \dots, \theta_M) p(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_M) d\theta_1, \dots, d\theta_M}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \cdots \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(\mathbf{y} | \theta_1, \dots, \theta_M) p(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_M) d\theta_1, \dots, d\theta_M} \quad (7)$$

we see that we must integrate the numerator over each of the i regions of interest as well as perform M additional integrations to obtain the denominator scale factor term. Accurate and efficient computation of P_i is achieved via Gaussian quadrature [5]. One-dimensional Gaussian quadrature makes the approximation [14], [16]

$$\int_a^b f(\theta_m) w(\theta_m) d\theta_m \approx \sum_{n=1}^N c_n f(\theta_m(n)), \quad (8)$$

where error goes to zero as N goes to infinity. For simplicity, we assume independent parameters such that the numerator in (7) factors into a product of M one-dimensional integrals

$$\int_{\theta_1 \in [a_{1,i}, b_{1,i}]} p(\mathbf{y} | \theta_1) p(\theta_1) d\theta_1 \cdots \int_{\theta_M \in [a_{M,i}, b_{M,i}]} p(\mathbf{y} | \theta_M) p(\theta_M) d\theta_M, \quad (9)$$

and likewise for the denominator. However, multi-dimensional quadrature techniques may be used for integrals of joint pdfs that do not factor. The choice of weight function $w(\theta_m) = 1$

Fig. 3. QBCSE Implementation.

and finite integral bounds leads to the choice of Gauss-Legendre rules. That is, N th-order Legendre polynomials are used to approximate the integrand with choice of N corresponding to desired accuracy. In this way, we use Gaussian quadrature to solve (5) with weights $w(\theta_m) = 1$ and functions $f(\theta_m) = p(\mathbf{y} | \theta_m) p(\theta_m)$. The coefficients $\{c_n\}$ are defined by the Legendre polynomials and are available in numerical form from references such as [15] and [17]. These integral solutions enable the calculation of the posterior density $p(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathbf{y})$, which is then used to find estimates (e.g. MAP or credible set) of the underlying signal parameters.

Alternatively, MAP estimates are typically found by sampling the numerator term of the posterior pdf. Normalization to acquire the associated probability is generally done by dividing by the sum of the sampled numerator terms, which is equivalent to a Riemann sum integration to estimate (1). Analysis in [6] shows up to twelve orders of magnitude improvement in computing the posterior probability using Gaussian quadrature versus sampling, with relatively little (no more than 11 times) additional computational burden. However, the analysis in [6] assumes the sampling method is uniformly sampling the correct region of the probability space. In practice, and especially in multiple dimensions, efficient choice of sample points may miss regions of high probability. Section IV-B compares random sampling with QBCSE.

B. Application of Interest

So far, we have discussed observations \mathbf{y} and parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ in general terms. Now, let us focus on an application of estimating parameters from attributed radar scattering models. For scattering models such as those in [7], [18], the observed data $\mathbf{y} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}\{\mathbf{S}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\} \\ \text{Im}\{\mathbf{S}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\} \end{bmatrix}_{2K \times 1}$ may be described as a vector of the real and imaginary parts of the radar phase history $\mathbf{S}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ plus zero-mean white Gaussian noise. That is,

$$p(\mathbf{y} | \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \right)^{2K} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{S}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|^2 \right\}. \quad (10)$$

$\mathbf{S}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is a nonlinear function of the parameters, and estimation of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ becomes a multi-dimensional non-convex optimization.

The posterior pdf may be multi-modal since multiple parameter sets may map to similar observations, as shown in [10]. Thus, we find estimation of credible sets a desirable approach to identify all “true”, “feasible”, and “confuser” parameters that correspond to the observed data. In this paper, we demonstrate the CSE approach for estimating parameters in the canonical shape models of [7].

Priors $p(\theta)$ are picked based on radar measurement capabilities and physical scene practicalities. For example, object lengths must be greater than zero and less than the scene extent. Results in Section IV assume uniform priors, so both the numerator and denominator in (7) have finite integration limits.

C. Fast Computation

As described above and in Figure 3, the zoom-in approach to locating regions of large probability mass provides a practical computational approach to credible set estimation. For additional computational speed-up, we first utilized a graphics processing unit (GPU) with a CUDA interface within Matlab. With the GPU, we reduced the time for several hundred million computations from several hours on a PC to a few seconds [5]. Recently, we have implemented parallel computations on Spirit, an Air Force Research Laboratory Department of Defense Supercomputing Resource Center system, to overcome memory limitations on a single GPU [6].

D. Defining the Credible Set

Equation (4) defines the credible set as the area of the posterior pdf of that integrates to $1 - \alpha$. In practice, we cannot expect that the probability masses sum exactly to the prescribed accuracy $1 - \alpha$. We sort the pmf values P_i for the desired “zoom”, given by the sub-ILIs. Due to discretization of parameter space, we include intervals of parameter values, corresponding to the sub-ILIs, in the credible set, rather than individual points. We form the credible set by including the largest (sorted) P_i 's up to and including the P_i that pushes $\sum_i P_i$ over the $1 - \alpha$ threshold. The credible set formed this way has at most one ‘extra’ probability mass, making it slightly too big but still meeting the desired confidence level.

IV. RESULTS

CSE allows us to find disjoint regions in parameter space, corresponding to ambiguous or equivalent parameter sets that have high probability, rather than choosing a single, high-probability peak. Quadrature integration allows us to efficiently compute the probabilities associated with the CS. Here, we demonstrate the methods discussed in Sections II-III for estimating parameters in the radar canonical shape scattering models of [7]. We start by demonstrating the QBCSE. Then, we compare QBCSE to random sampling (RS).

A. QBCSE Examples

To demonstrate QBCSE, radar phase history observations \mathbf{y} are generated by adding white Gaussian noise to the assumed scattering model $\mathcal{S}(\theta)$. Radar parameters for Figure 4 are as

follows: 300 MHz carrier frequency, 100 MHz bandwidth, 37.5° elevation, -5° to $+5^\circ$ azimuth in 1° steps, noise variance 0.25. The example in Figure 4 consists of a single plate scatterer with position parameters $x = 5$ m, $y = 6$ m, $z = 0$ m, size parameters length $L = 6$ m, height $H = 2$ m, and orientation parameters roll = 5° , pitch = 20° , and yaw = 0° . The example in Figure 5 includes two identical plates with parameters as in the single plate case but with one plate at $x = 5$ m and one at $x = 5.5$ m. The radar parameters for Figure 5 use a wider aperture $\pm 90^\circ$ and noise variance of 0.01. For both cases, uniform priors are chosen. In Figures 4 and 5, only the plotted parameters are treated as unknowns; the remaining plate parameters are set to the true values.

Figure 4 shows the benefit of the multi-zoom approach. The multi-zoom approach quickly reduces a $50 \text{ m} \times 50 \text{ m}$ search space to a $2 \text{ m} \times 2 \text{ m}$ space. The parameter space is first discretized into 1 m ILIs from 0 m to 50 m for the length parameter L and 1 m ILIs from 0 m to 50 m for the height parameter H . P_i is computed for each ILI using Gauss-Legendre quadrature with polynomial order $N = 5$. The pmf for the region $[1 \text{ m} \leq L < 2 \text{ m}, 5 \text{ m} \leq H < 6 \text{ m}]$ evaluates to one, indicating that ILI contains all probable parameter values. At this coarse zoom, a polynomial order of $N = 5$ is not sufficient to accurately locate the correct HPD interval but allows us to narrow the search space. Therefore, we zoom to 0.1 m ILIs for a region $0 \text{ m} \leq L \leq 10 \text{ m}$ and $0 \text{ m} \leq H \leq 10 \text{ m}$ that has some buffer around the predicted peak. At 0.1 m zoom, we find that the most probable parameter values are in the region $[6.1 \text{ m} \leq L < 6.2 \text{ m}, 1.9 \text{ m} \leq H < 2.0 \text{ m}]$. Next, computing P_i 's on 0.01 m ILIs, we see the shape of the posterior take form. The peak of the estimated posterior corresponds to the quadrature-based MAP estimate, which is near the true parameter location. Many parameters near the peak location have similarly high probabilities and may be within the resolution limits of the radar, so we capture them in the CS. The 95% confidence CS is shown in Figure 8 and consists of the 0.01 m parameter ILIs that comprise the largest HPD values summing to just over 0.95.

Figure 5 further shows the utility of (QB)CSE. In this example, the range location x is estimated for two plates, whose parameters are identical with the exception of x . Without additional rules to label each plate, there are two possible solutions: plate one is at $x = 5$ m and plate two is at $x = 5.5$ m or vice versa. The posterior probability includes two disjoint regions of high probability at $(x_1, x_2) = (5, 5.5)$ and $(x_1, x_2) = (5.5, 5)$. Upon sorting the largest P_i values, ILIs from both regions are included in the 95% credible set. Both solutions are feasible. MAP estimation would choose a single largest point, which would be one of the two peaks (and may be the wrong one!) depending on numerical precision. Therefore, the CSE provides the ATR algorithm with feasible estimates near the truth as well as confusers. The labeling example in Figure 5 is used for illustration; however, when there exists a many-to-one mapping from parameter to observation space, the confuser parameters would be captured in the same manner using the (QB)CSE.

(a) Iteration 1: 1 m intervals

(b) Iteration 2: 0.1 m intervals

(c) Iteration 3: 0.01 m intervals

Fig. 4. The estimate of length L and height H parameters for a canonical plate scatterer is found by computing (5) using decreasing ILI sizes $[\alpha_i, b_i]$ as each QBCSE iteration zooms in on regions of high probability. Probabilities listed are for the largest mass at each iteration. The corresponding 95% confidence credible set is depicted as shaded boxes in Figure 8.

B. QBCSE Compared to Random Sampling

Ultimately, we wish to apply QBCSE to feature extraction for radar ATR of vehicles. Civilian vehicles contain a double-bounce scatterer between the vehicle's side and the ground as well as a single-bounce cylinder scattering mechanism from the vehicle roofline [19]. Because we can neither report the posterior or credible set efficiently for the $M = 8^Q$ dimension required to estimate Q dihedral and cylinder type canonical scatterers from [7], we revisit the example in Figure 4 to compare QBCSE with a random sampling (RS) method.

QBCSE is run once for a given data set, and the associated MAP estimate (i.e. the 100% credible set, or peak interval) is shown to have low mean absolute error (MAE). Alternatively, many realizations of RS must be averaged to achieve low

(a) Posterior pmf

(b) Credible set for $\alpha = 0.95$

Fig. 5. Scatterer label ambiguity leads to a disjoint 95% confidence credible set for the range position x parameter of two identical plates.

estimation error. In practice, one would like to take as few samples per realization and as few realizations as possible to minimize computation time and maximize accuracy. Figure 6 shows the MAE for the RS MAP estimate versus the number of samples used, reported as a percentage of the 40401 QBCSE intervals in Figure 4(c). The results in Figure 6 are averaged over 2500 realizations of randomly sampling the posterior pdf (and simple normalization via Riemann sum with equal weights). Figure 6 indicates that more realizations of RS are needed to achieve error performance as low as QBCSE.

Figure 7 plots the RS MAP MAE as a function of number of realizations for various sample percentages. Figure 7 shows that convergence of the RS method is slow, and many more realizations will be needed to achieve the QBCSE MAP error.

Figure 8 shows the 95% credible set found via QBCSE (HPD set for Figure 4) as shaded boxes. RS error ellipses are shown for several percent sampling cases. The error ellipses are in good agreement with the credible set; however, RS was averaged 2500 times to achieve those errors. A single realization of RS may not even sample the immediate region around the true parameters, as indicated by the black dots in Figure 8 for one realization of the credible set found via RS.

Figures 6-8 show that the large number of samples and large number of realizations for the RS method to achieve low error requires far more computations than one run of QBCSE.

V. CONCLUSION

We have presented QBCSE and applied it to canonical feature extraction for radar ATR. We have implemented a Gauss

Fig. 6. Average parameter estimation error for random sampling method increases as the number of samples decreases.

Fig. 8. The credible set contains the HPD set, whereas a given realization of RS may miss the peak entirely.

Fig. 7. For this example, RS method does not achieve the QB MAP error for less than 2500 realizations \times 40401 samples/realization.

quadrature method and multi-zoom approach for efficiently and accurately estimating the posterior pdf and subsequent CS. Results demonstrate the increase in information contained in a CSE over traditional MAP estimate. One could argue that the posterior pdf contains all the likelihood information, so the posterior pdf is all that is really needed. However, CSE distills the posterior pdf down to a set of highest probability points, providing a principled means for interpreting the information contained in the posterior pdf, while capturing multiple feasible solutions that a point estimator such as MAP would discard. Furthermore, QBCSE is computationally more efficient than RS for accurate computation of the posterior pdf and MAP estimates. the quadrature approach is feasible to implement in several dimensions. Future research will increase the dimensionality of the search space (we have computed up to 5D in [6]) and apply the QBCSE approach to extract features from civilian vehicle data.

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